

RAMONES

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

Deliverable

**Document ID: D5.10 Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities
no1**

31/01/2022

RAMONES funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 FET Proactive programme via grant agreement No.101017808

Document Info

Project Information			
Acronym	RAMONES		
Name	Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems		
Start Date	1 Jan 2021	End Date	31 Dec 2024
Program	H2020-EU.1.2.2. - FET Proactive		
Call ID	H2020-FETPROACT-2020-2	Topic	FETPROACT-EIC-08-2020 - Environmental Intelligence
Grant No	101017808	Instrument	RIA
Document Information			
Document Id	D5.10		
Document Title	Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no1		
Due Date	31-Dec-2021	Delivery Date	31-01-2022
Lead Beneficiary	NKUA(1)		
Beneficiaries (part.)	NKUA (1), IST-ID (2), EVOL (3), ENS (4), NTUA (5), PLOA (6), UDUR (7), UCA (8)		
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Reviewer(s)	Valsamis Ntouskos (NTUA)		
Workpackages	WP5 - Citizen Awareness, Dissemination and Communication Activities		
Version	V1.0	Stage	Submitted
Distribution	Public		
Keywords	Dissemination, Communication, Environmental Intelligence, Social Media, Conferences, Peer-reviewed papers, Fairs	Type	DEC

Document Change Record

Version	Date	Change Description	Editor	Change Location (page/section)
0.1	20.12.2021	Template adopted, structure defined	Theodoros Mertzimekis (NKUA)	
0.5	25.12.2021	First draft version of the document	Theodoros Mertzimekis (NKUA)	
0.9	27.01.2020	Comments and references provided by the deliverable contributors	Antonio Pascoal, Pedro Batista, Aggelos Mallios, Konstantinos Karantzas	
0.8	27.01.2022	Comments received by the reviewer	Valsamis Ntouskos	
1.0	31.01.2022	Document version submitted to EC	Theodoros Mertzimekis (NKUA)	

Disclaimer

RAMONES is a European Innovation Council (EIC) FET Proactive project in the Environmental Intelligence Scope B, related to radically novel approaches to resilient, reliable and environmentally responsible in-situ monitoring, funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 FET proactive programme, via grant agreement No. 101017808.

RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity gap in sampling needs and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. These goals will be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy. It will also design new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AUV	Autonomous Underwater Vehicle
BRID	Blue Research and Innovation Days
CAMS	Control Applications in Marine Systems, Robotics, and Vehicles
CITM	Centre for Innovation and Technology Management
E&A	Electronics & Automation
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EIC	European Innovation Council
EMRA	EU-funded Marine Robotics and Applications
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
EUMR	EU Merge Control
FIC.A	Festival Internacional de Ciência
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GI-PSS	Green Investment Policy Support System
HNPS	Hellenic Nuclear Physics Society
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IFAC	International Federation of Automatic Control
ISIM	International Symposium on Internet of Things (IoT) and Machine Learning (ML)
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
OTF	Outreach Task Force
RSS	Really Simple Syndication service
SoA	State of the Art
WP	Work Package

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Abstract

RAMONES is an ambitious, high-risk project which aims to prove that innovative combination and advancement of recent developments in detector technology and sensor materials, low-power-autonomous robotic systems, and process-modeling theories, have the potential to overcome contemporary limitations and open the window to high temporal and spatial resolution underwater radioactivity measurements, in situ and in near real time, forming a game changer in deep-water environmental monitoring. RAMONES proposes a new generation of submarine radiation-sensing instruments, assisted by State of the Art (SoA) robotic and artificial intelligence (AI) solutions towards understanding radiation related risks near and far from coastal areas, while providing data for the international community towards shaping new policies and governance guidelines for environmental sustainability, economic growth and human health. RAMONES will provide tools for long-term, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, propose new AI-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these can be achieved by combining SoA equipment from various disciplines in well-balanced synergy, and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. Additionally, one of the main goals is to introduce novel ways of monitoring and response channels to inform key socio-political stakeholders at regular intervals from medium (daily, weekly) to low (monthly to inter-annually) frequencies.

This document is a dissemination, outreach, and liaison activities report, describing the first-period activities and achievements in the scope of WP5 of the RAMONES project.

The work carried out so far in the WP5 framework has focused on three main objectives:

- Communication / to Increase RAMONES visibility in terms of activities and outcomes, receive valuable feedback, inform the society and engage potentially interested stakeholders with RAMONES technology and innovation deliverables
- Dissemination / to position RAMONES as a top-rank European EIC project, extend its range of applications and generate potential for new synergies across various disciplines (marine radioactivity studies, marine science, marine robotics, AI, natural hazards risk analysis and more) and commercial exploitation.
- User engagement and outreach / to share knowledge for further development and optimization of the considered technology services, raise awareness, and demonstrate how RAMONES can cater to the needs and thematic end-user requirements.

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The outreach task force (OTF) has been in permanent and close contact with the entire consortium, managing the knowledge and project activities for communication, dissemination and engagement purposes. The activity is organized by means of four tasks to be carried out throughout the life of the project (M1 to M48) on a recurring basis: (i) communication, dissemination and outreach activities, (ii) branding, online presence and material establishment, (iii) stakeholder's engagement and (iv) Environmental Intelligence initiatives and other liaison activities (such as reaching out to future collaborators, scientific communities and governmental agencies) with the support of all the partners according to their field of knowledge, specialty and connection with the ecosystem.

The document presents:

- The work plan for the work package, with goals and planned tasks
- The report of activities carried out during the period, considering the digital channels, the material and templates, the articles and publications, the events and activities organized and participated, and the Environmental/Radioactivity/Robotics-domain oriented activities
- The WP5 organization
- The established KPIs and outreach and dissemination activities

1. WP5 / Dissemination & Communication Tasks

1.1 WP Objectives related to Dissemination and Communication

The objectives of WP5 which are relevant to the Citizen Awareness, Dissemination and Communication Activities are: (i) to establish a visual and textually recognizable impression of the project and its work; (ii) to maximise the impactful visibility of project's work and achievements; (iii) to engage stakeholders that can support sustainability of the project via both update and feedback provisioning and can further empower the vision around the scientific domain communities, and (iv) to provide essential information and knowledge on the RAMONES project to 3rd parties activating esp. in H2020 and Environmental Intelligence landscape.

The WP is organized into six (6) tasks, from which the four (4) most relevant to the dissemination and outreach activities are presented below (T5.3-5.6).

1.2 WP Tasks

Below are presented the tasks to be carried out, according to the grant agreement (GA).

1.2.1 T5.3 Raising Citizens Awareness, Dissemination, Communication and Outreach activities

The task started with a contribution to the Deliverable D5.9 with regards to Raising Citizens Awareness, Dissemination, Communication and Outreach activities. The document outlines the vision, strategy, and a plan of opportunities, targets and outcomes and baseline dissemination material related to the RAMONES project, in combination with the work of T5.5, on stakeholder identification and targeting. The plan, constantly updated, is the road map for the activities of the work package in all directions. The task defines the OTF and assigns responsibilities for supervising and conducting activities. It also includes:

- Assignment and quality reviewing of blog posts and press releases that will be generated by invitation to respective project teams and partners.
- Track and report on the project of work, in foreseen reports as well as in internal meetings.
- Guidelines to contribute to the relevant best practices essay issued by the WP participants.
- Production of interviews or webcasts on projects activities and achievements.
- Production of multimedia presentations with selection and editing of content provided by technical, business and research activities of the project.
- Produce project's newsletter on at least an annual basis.

- Delivery of scientific publications.

The task 5.3 is led by NKUA with the support of all the partners.

The task progressed appropriately according to the evolution of the project. The content generation and review model have been defined, both of technical-scientific and general informative nature, and they have been published on the different platforms and on the RAMONES website. The multimedia content, including demonstrators or broad-spectrum presentations, have been uploaded to the YouTube channel and promoted from all RAMONES digital channels and social media.

1.2.2 T5.3 Branding, online presence and material establishment

The task started with the delivery of visual and textual representation of the project to be used in project dissemination activities, considering the website, the digital channels, face to face or online presentations, events, as well as printed ones. It also delivered guidelines for promotion and use of the delivered materials, as well as some guides and training material for its use. Apart from templates, the task delivered early in the project lifetime generic material for reuse in several face to face, printed and on-line occasions and in several languages. This material evolves in the course of the project, both for renewal of the project “face” but also as material matures around the deliveries of the technical and business work packages. The task included:

- steps to establish the website of the project, apply the branding of the project on its visuals, and maintain it for the duration of the project.
- establish 4 social media platform presence points, style them, monitoring and granting access as required.
- establish and operate mailing lists for newsletter, general and targeted communication.
- deliver and maintain templates for various documents and activities according to the needs.
- deliver baseline, generic content in the form of posters, leaflets and textual components.

The task is led by NKUA with the support of all RAMONES partners.

All the activities pertaining to this task were carried out adequately during the reported period, carrying out all the updates and revisions that the needs of the project, as well as its partners required.

1.2.3 T5.5 Citizens and Stakeholders engagement and Networking

The task started with the layout of an effective stakeholder engagement plan that allowed RAMONES to locate and engage the targeted audience defined in the Communication, Dissemination, Engagement and outreach Plan and influencing individuals. The activities for engagement of stakeholders utilized the instruments provided by T5.4, that include, but are not limited to, email and web-based communication (focus on social media), generic promotion material, participation in events and conferences etc.

Furthermore, they expand on those with stakeholder-targeted

- material produced jointly with other project's work package teams able to address a specific audience,
- events (workshops, sessions in conferences, meetings) planned for specific groups
- establishment of interactions with key persons representing influential movements and organizations.

The task established the means for disseminating information inside the project, and mainly via internal reports and meeting sessions, the work completed with stakeholders. In addition, the task seeks to draw substantial feedback from them to empower the project's activities. The process was largely boosted by the Environmental Intelligence activities and participation to relevant events such as to the Kickoff meetings of every of the Pathfinder projects, meetings in the framework of EIC collaborations, participation to the GoodIT2021 Conference (presented below), etc.

The task also liaises with OpenAIRE and Open Science activities for the most efficient possible liaison to the current strategies and methodologies suggested.

This task is led by NKUA with the support of IST-ID, ENS, NTUA and PLOA.

The global coronavirus pandemic (still strong and active) impacted on face-to-face events, and many activities evolved towards digital. Attendance and participation in events, congresses, exhibitions, fairs and others was changed to virtual and the meetings were moved online. The main concern was the capacity to interact with individuals, resolved by the activity of thematic partners and their ability to involve their ecosystem and the ability of scientific partners to establish collaborations with other projects and initiatives.

The above tasks are of high relevance with the tasks 5.1 and 5.2 namely T5.1 *Forecasting and risk management*, and T5.2 *Raising Awareness / Supporting policymaking concerning the citizen and policy makers awareness*.

1.2.4 T5.6 Task for Cross-project collaborations

This task aims at establishing synergies and co-operation across projects on highly related topics, in particular those stemming from the same Call and funded under the topic of Environmental Intelligence (I-SEED, RAMONES, RESET, WATCHPLANT and SMARTLAGOON).

The overall goals are:

- to provide a joint vision and blueprint for Environmental Intelligence, and
- to foster the interdisciplinary communities that are driving Environmental Intelligence forward, as well as improving the visibility for all key stakeholders.

Examples of activities to be jointly undertaken are: (a) Organizing relevant mailing lists for the research communities, policy makers, stakeholders, exchange and collaboration with related projects, in particular those stemming from the same call and funded under the same sub-topic as the present one; (b) Based on the Open Science and FAIR data policies outcomes and best practices networking activities such as common seminars and workshops; (c) a joint blueprint for a full-fledged system for environmental intelligence (e.g. updated deliverable each year); (d) Joint publications (e.g. proceedings joining best papers after 3 years and 4 years); (e) Organization of joint events and capacity-building activities: summer schools, joint workshops; and (f) Joint participation in meetings and events organized by the EIC or other (e.g., relevant science and technology gatherings).

RAMONES has actively participated in a wave of joint meetings (project Kick-Off meetings, collaboration meetings, meetings with the EIC officers) to promote the main objectives of the task related to Environmental Intelligence, which will continue over the full lifetime of the project (till M48). A common path for collaboration has been agreed among the projects and the first joint deliverables has been submitted (D5.18 Plan for cross-project collaboration and D5.19 Vision and Blueprint for Environmental Intelligence in Europe no1).

In addition, RAMONES has invested time, effort and funding to promote Environmental Intelligence at all actions involving dissemination, communication and outreach. The official RAMONES website, social media and digital channels promote the joint effort and feature relevant keywords and content.

See also §2.5 for more details on the links with the H2020 projects participating in the joint activities.

1.3 Deliverables Planning

The project kick-off was the official launch of dissemination activities, presenting the first generation of templates and organization of committees.

1.3.1 Deliverables Description

The deliverables of WP5 that are related to Dissemination, Communication and Outreach are detailed below, specifying its codification, title and description:

- D5.9 Raise Awareness, Communication, Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement & Exploitation Plan, report on vision, strategy, and draft plan of opportunities, targets and outcomes expected and baseline dissemination material – regularly updated after delivery. Plan and materialize the exploitation of results for commercial purposes and public policy making.
- D5.10 Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no1, report on yearly activities concerning the promotion of the project together with the results and feedback obtained by our audience / counterparts.
- D5.11 Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no2, report on yearly activities concerning the promotion of the project together with the results and feedback obtained by our audience / counterparts.
- D5.12 Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no3, report on yearly activities concerning the promotion of the project together with the results and feedback obtained by our audience / counterparts.
- D5.13 Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no4, report on yearly activities concerning the promotion of the project together with the results and feedback obtained by our audience / counterparts.
- D5.14 Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no1, report on the details of the 1st period various promotional materials, branding scheme and visual promotion.
- D5.15 Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no2, report on the details of the 2nd period various promotional materials, branding scheme and visual promotion.
- D5.16 Report on Outreach and Liaison Activities no1, report on 1st period activities and achievements of WP (2 years report).
- D5.17 Report on Outreach and Liaison Activities no2, report on 1st period activities and achievements of WP (2 years report).
- D5.18 Plan for cross-project collaboration, report on collaboration of Environmental Intelligence projects.

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- D5.19 Vision and Blueprint for Environmental Intelligence in Europe no1, report on yearly developments on Environmental Intelligence and key challenges and the solutions adopted so far by the five projects.
- D5.20 Vision and Blueprint for Environmental Intelligence in Europe no2, report on yearly developments on Environmental Intelligence and key challenges and the solutions adopted so far by the five projects.
- D5.21 Vision and Blueprint for Environmental Intelligence in Europe no3, report on yearly developments on Environmental Intelligence and key challenges and the solutions adopted so far by the five projects.
- D5.22 Vision and Blueprint for Environmental Intelligence in Europe no4, report on yearly developments on Environmental Intelligence and key challenges and the solutions adopted so far by the five projects.
- D5.23 Website, social media, report on site and social networks with visual alignment to the strategy with initial content

1.3.2 Deliverables timeline

The scheduling for deliverables is presented in the following table. It is worth stressing that all deliverables are public and will be disseminated openly via the RAMONES website once finalized.

Table 1 WP5 planning related to Dissemination/Communication.

Code	Deliverable Title	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Month
D5.9	Raise Awareness, Communication, Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement & Exploitation Plan	UDUR	Report	Public	4
D5.10	Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no1	NKUA	Report	Public	12
D5.11	Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no2	NKUA	Report	Public	24
D5.12	Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no3	NKUA	Report	Public	36
D5.13	Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no4	NKUA	Report	Public	48
D5.14	Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no1	NKUA	Websites, patents filling, etc.	Public	8
D5.15	Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no2	NKUA	Websites, patents filling, etc.	Public	18

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D5.16	Report on Outreach and Liaison Activities no1	UDUR	Report	Public	24
D5.17	Report on Outreach and Liaison Activities no2	UDUR	Report	Public	48
D5.18	Plan for cross-project collaboration	NKUA	Report	Public	6
D5.19	Vision and Blueprint for Environmental Intelligence in Europe no1	NKUA	Report	Public	12
D5.20	Vision and Blueprint for Environmental Intelligence in Europe no2	NKUA	Report	Public	24
D5.21	Vision and Blueprint for Environmental Intelligence in Europe no3	NKUA	Report	Public	36
D5.22	Vision and Blueprint for Environmental Intelligence in Europe no4	NKUA	Report	Public	48
D5.23	Website, Social Media	NKUA	Websites, patents filling, etc.	Public	1

2. Report of activities

2.1 Digital channels

2.1.1 RAMONES project website

RAMONES established a dedicated website for the project (<https://ramones-project.eu/>), applying the branding of the project on its visuals and keeping it updated considering both the content and the new features and integrations. The purpose of the website is to proactively promote the project, become a reference point of knowledge and also a content hub, as well as promote the project results by providing targeted information to various audiences within and beyond the project scientific community.

The design and development of RAMONES' website was presented in a specific deliverable belonging to the same WP5. The web project was presented in the document "D5.23 Website, Social Media" on M1.

The RAMONES site presents all the information related to the RAMONES project, including:

- Information about the project: the aims and objectives, the challenges and the services to be offered.

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- Information about the consortium, the advisory board, the project approach as well as the Environmental Intelligence roadmap.
- Dissemination and open access content: Articles, blog, collaborations, research, dissemination material, press and media references, public outcomes, publications.
- Mailing & Newsletters access and management.
- Events held or planned, with updated information on fairs, exhibitions, congresses, webinars, workshops, etc.
- Training related to held or planned webinars, summer schools, hands-on practical training and internships.
- Synergies to other related projects and programs.
- Dedicated section to Environmental Intelligence in Europe concerning collaborations with other H2020 pathfinder projects.
- News, with the latest information and updates on press, posts, posters, editorials, events and other activities.
- Service information (Contact information, GDPR policy, Disclaimer, cookies policies, and more).

Figure 1 RAMONES website (home page).

The website also acts as a reference contact point for any person interested in the project, such as the general public, stakeholders, expert and non-expert audiences, providing a contact form as depicted below:

Figure 2 RAMONES website as a reference contact point.

From a technical perspective, the website also hosts useful tools and features, such as:

- Embedded links to RAMONES social networks accounts (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube).
- Really Simple Syndication service (RSS).
- Categories and tags of the content.
- Newsletter management: contact subscription, management of user subscription services.
- Connection to other Environmental Intelligence projects, affiliated projects and the consortium members.

The website has been technically maintained (backups, plugins, releases management, etc.) and frequently upgraded with new services as it became needed or requested.

Metrics

The website has been updated on a monthly basis, as illustrated in the figure below. The objective is for the website to be the focal point that collects and disseminates the main past or future events in the life of the project, but also provides a data-driven set of information on reaching out the online audience, including stakeholders, general audience etc.

Figure 3 Monthly website activity concerning users and sessions.

In Fig. 3, Month 1 corresponds to the initial website setup and launch. As the project activity grew, the website reflected upon all the work carried out.

The resulting figures reflect an intense, continuous and transversal work.

An analytics account was created to track website activity. As a result, it can be stated that RAMONES is well known in Europe and throughout the world. The following figures illustrate the impact of the RAMONES website, considering the country of access to the RAMONES website, the visitors per country and the number of sessions per country, respectively.

Figure 4 Main visitors to RAMONES website per country.

Figure 5 Distribution of website visitors per country.

Figure 6 Distribution of website sessions per country (top-20).

The following graph shows an overview of the evolution of the number of website sessions.

Figure 7 Website monthly sessions.

Finally, a cumulative curve of the new users per month shows that new users are constantly increasing.

Figure 8 New users per month cumulative curve.

2.1.2 Social media channels

RAMONES established five (5) social media platform presence points, granted access as required, and periodically tracked using tools built into each platform.

Social media channels have been constantly updated with relevant content, which makes them a cost-effective way to publicize, disseminate information about news, achievements or any relevant event in an easy and fast way and create awareness for the project. Accessible to anyone, the social platforms are aimed at innovators, researchers, scientists, ICT and domain oriented (radioactivity, robotics, marine engineers, geoscientists etc) specialists, stakeholders, policy makers, press, media, disseminators and the general public, promoting the achievements of the project at the exact moment something is happening.

A task of attracting and engaging followers is carried out, involving RAMONES partners that are encouraged to share the content and taking advantage of the events organized or participated by RAMONES and its project members (conferences, workshops, fairs, exhibitions, etc.). Joint activities with other projects are also a means of attracting users.

The social channels created for the project are Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube. In order to brand the project and for somebody to reach the channels, all of them have a common name (**ramones_eu**) and are aligned to the project identity principles.

Facebook

An official account for RAMONES has been created, managed and updated frequently on Facebook: **Ramones EU**. The next figure shows the main page.

Figure 9 RAMONES Facebook Home page.

Facebook allows reaching out to relevant groups through disseminating information about news, achievements or any relevant event in an easy and quick way with more detailed information on messages in relation to other social media channels.

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The following figure is an example and illustrates a representative publication.

Figure 10 RAMONES messages in Facebook (samples).

From Facebook, RAMONES also communicates with several scientific groups and other projects of similar interests and facilitates the promotion of activities and events.

Instagram

The official account of the project on Instagram is: **ramones_eu**. The main page is shown below.

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Figure 11 RAMONES Instagram Home page.

The account is used to attract followers of different fields by the power of pictures that are accompanied by a short text. Sneak peeks are also released through Instagram stories.

Twitter

An official account for RAMONES has been created, managed and updated on Twitter: **ramones_eu**. The next figure shows the main page.

Figure 12 RAMONES Twitter profile page.

The account has been used for short and quick messages to keep the audience up-to-date on the activities, news and achievements, allowing them to interact with RAMONES and offering them access to all the additional information on the website. Twitter has also been the best channel to connect with relevant stakeholders (including other European and H2020 projects) for cross promotion.

Twitter served both to communicate project content and to interact with other users/agents and be endorsed by third parties, as well as to interact and engage the team, as it is illustrated in the next samples.

Figure 13 Sample RAMONES tweet showcasing research results.

Figure 14 RAMONES project quoted and endorsed by other accounts on Twitter.

LinkedIn

A RAMONES account has been created, managed and updated on LinkedIn: **RAMONES_EU project**. The next figure shows the main page.

Figure 15 RAMONES LinkedIn public page.

LinkedIn is more career-oriented than the other accounts and is used to connect with other researchers, business organizations and research institutes relevant to RAMONES objectives and vision.

The following figure is an example and illustrates a representative publication.

Figure 16 RAMONES post on LinkedIn group (sample).

YouTube channel

An official channel for RAMONES was created, managed and updated on YouTube: **project ramones_eu**. The main page is depicted in the following figure.

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Figure 17 RAMONES channel on YouTube.

The channel hosts multimedia content, including presentations, demos, training material and later on recorded webinars and other scientific videos. The following figure is an example and illustrates a representative video.

Figure 18 RAMONES video on YouTube channel highlighting key issues in the project.

Tracking and metrics

RAMONES activity in social networks is continuous, both in the generation of content and in the interaction with followers and stakeholders. As a result, a high impact has been achieved, both in the scientific audience and in the general public, as illustrated in the following figures.

On Facebook, an average of 4 posts per month were published, during a 12-month period (M1-M12) with overall good impression and interaction indices.

Figure 19 Summary of Facebook activity from the start of the project.

Statistics about the age and gender of the followers on Facebook draw interesting inferences from the audience. The Total number of followers is 462.

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Figure 20 An estimation of the Facebook followers per gender.

The metrics also concern the impact of the posts to the Facebook users as well as the views of the page per month.

Figure 21 On average, the total number of Facebook users that impacted our posts per month.

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Figure 22 Total views per month.

On Instagram, a total of 23 posts were published the first year of the project having sufficient interactions and 70 followers stay informed about our news.

Figure 23 Instagram impression from the start of the (project per month).

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On Twitter, 65 tweets have been published on a monthly average during M1-M12, highly exceeding the project objectives and many retweets respectively. The page has 70 active followers and several other users that react to our tweets.

Following is the monthly Twitter analytics for the period M1-M12.

Your Tweets earned **2.8K impressions** over this **31 day period**

Your Tweets earned **2.6K impressions** over this **28 day period**

Your Tweets earned **1.9K impressions** over this **31 day period**

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Your Tweets earned **2.8K impressions** over this **30 day period**

Your Tweets earned **1.5K impressions** over this **31 day period**

Your Tweets earned **515 impressions** over this **30 day period**

Your Tweets earned **2.2K impressions** over this **31 day period**

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Your Tweets earned **723 impressions** over this **31 day** period

Your Tweets earned **2.0K impressions** over this **30 day** period

Your Tweets earned **324 impressions** over this **31 day** period

Your Tweets earned **524 impressions** over this **30 day** period

Your Tweets earned **408 impressions** over this **22 day** period

Figure 24 Monthly Twitter analytics for the @ramones_eu account (01.01.2021-22.12.2021).

On M12, 18.294 tweet impressions have been achieved, already exceeding the goal of 10.000 of social media impressions established by the end of the project. The figure below shows the monthly evolution.

Figure 25 RAMONES monthly tweet impressions.

Figure 26 RAMONES monthly tweets and retweets.

The analysis of the number of impressions to RAMONES twitter profile is an indication of how the project triggers interest, as well as the extent to which it is becoming known. The impact is closely linked to relevant events (such as the International Fair of Thessaloniki, participation in events and congresses, Southampton Fair and Open Day in Lisbon).

Due to the global coronavirus pandemic, all face-to-face activities have been severely restricted. To overcome this limitation, all the digital channels of the project have been strengthened and online activity has been strongly reinforced.

All the previous figures show the results obtained. The following figure illustrates the impact obtained compared to what was planned at the beginning of the project under normal conditions.

On LinkedIn, a total of 13 posts were published during the 11-month period (M2-M12) having 63 likes. The total views of the platform are 2.132 and the followers until today are 69. Following is a sample of 3 posts metrics of the LinkedIn platform.

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Your post posted on December 23, 2021
4 reactions

256 views

ITE

12 people from ITE viewed your post

National & Kapodistrian University of Athens	4
Ethnikon kai Kapodistriakon Panepistimion Athinon	3
Institute of Molecular Science- ICMol	2
University of Athens	2
Universidad de Alcalá	2
Hellenic Statistical Authority (ELSTAT)	1
Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution	1

Trophy

11 people who have the title Research Fellow viewed your post

Laboratory Scientist	9
Student	5
University Professor	4
School Teacher	3
Geologist	3
Product Researcher	3
Project Manager	2
Business Intelligence Consultant	1

Location Pin

36 people viewed your post from Athens Metropolitan Area

Greater Valencia Metropolitan Area	14
Greater Madrid Metropolitan Area	6
Greater Girona Area	2
Greater Oxford Area	1
Greater Paris Metropolitan Region	1
The Randstad, Netherlands	1
Stockholm Metropolitan Area	1
Frankfurt Rhine-Main Metropolitan Area	1

Figure 27 Sample post metrics.

On YouTube, 3 video posts have been uploaded which have 29 total views. The following pictures show the metrics of YouTube, such as total views and total impressions.

Figure 28 Total views.

Figure 29 Total impressions.

Finally, Twitter and Facebook are the main social media platforms that gather the most followers and impressions. LinkedIn, Instagram and YouTube are not as widespread as the other platforms are.

2.1.3 Mailing & Newsletter

RAMONES established and operated a mailing list for newsletters for general and targeted communication.

Management

The management of the contact list is organized from the RAMONES website. From a dedicated page, the mail services are offered to the audience, complying with the requirements of GDPR.

Management of personal preferences (update, unsubscribe) can also be completed from any email sent, which includes the information and a link in the footer.

The next figure illustrates the subscription form to the RAMONES newsletter.

The screenshot shows the RAMONES website's newsletter subscription page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'THE APPROACH', 'ENVIRONMENTAL INTELLIGENCE', 'TRAINING', 'EVENTS', and 'PUBLICATIONS', along with a 'Get in touch' button. Below this, the page is divided into sections for 'National Technical University of Athens', 'engineering marine science', 'University Business School', and 'Laboratoire de Physique de Clermont'. The central focus is a subscription form with the text 'Subscribe to the RAMONES Newsletter to be informed on our latest news!' and a 'Your Email' input field with a 'Join' button. The footer contains contact information, social media links, and a menu.

Figure 30 Subscription form to RAMONES Newsletter from RAMONES website.

Newsletters

Two newsletters have been published in the first year of the project (M09 and M12), complying with the committed biannual rate. The production of newsletters includes the design of templates, IT configuration and integrations, the edition of content and the user management. The topics have been studied with the participation of all partners, presenting achievements,

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news, participation in events, general and scientific information and much more, considering the needs of the project stage.

General information about the project and the members was also provided.

The following images illustrate the released newsletters. At the point of authoring this report, the number of subscribers has reached ~450, with a relative increase of ~15% after the publication of the first newsletter.

Ramones Kick-Off Meeting

An exciting moment for RAMONES as the project reaches its first Milestone (MS1) which is the official Kick-Off Meeting. The Meeting is taking place fully online due to the pandemic restrictions on Monday 22nd and Tuesday 23rd of March 2021. Please read the full agenda in the attached PDF file. Ramones Kick-Off Meeting

[Read more →](#)

Five EU projects join forces to develop an Environmental Intelligence system

The collaboration agreement between 5 EIC Pathfinder/FET Proactive projects has been signed. Its main aim is to deliver a blueprint for a full-fledged system for environmental intelligence. The main goal of Environmental Intelligence call (FETPROACT-EIC-08-2020) is to build a systemic understanding of the socio-environmental inter-relationships, to regulate or design policies and incentives for environmental sustainability...

[Read more →](#)

RAMONES in Blue Research and Innovation Days

RAMONES actively participates in the whole week (19-23 April 2021) of Blue Research and Innovation Days! During the first day, EU representatives and National Governmental and Regional representatives and Academic and Research Centers directors present the strategy and policies for Blue Economy. A dedicated workshop with presentations from new projects took place on Friday was...

[Read more →](#)

EMRA2021
Workshop on EU-funded
Marine Robotics and Applications
July 7-8, 2021 - Pisa (virtual)

RAMONES @EMRA2021

The RAMONES consortium participated in the EMRA2021, the Workshop where EU-funded Projects related to Marine Robotics and Applications present their vision and results. The limitations due to the pandemic resulted in the organization of a full online event, organized by ISME, the Italian Interuniversity Center of Integrated Systems for the Marine Environment. EMRA2021 was held...

[Read more →](#)

Figure 31 RAMONES 1st Newsletter (extract).

Finally, an excerpt from the footers of the RAMONES newsletter, common to any release:

Find us online

Be the first to receive valuable insights and scientific nuggets from RAMONES! We are always interested in your views. Reply to this email if you have any queries about the content of this newsletter, or anything else.

RAMONES receives funding from European Union under Horizon 2020 FET Proactive Programme via grant agreement No. 101017808

Figure 32 RAMONES Newsletter footer.

2.2 Material and templates

2.2.1 RAMONES identity

The first step was to create a digital identity and branding for RAMONES by means of logos:

Figure 33 RAMONES logos.

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The RAMONES logo has the form of a seal with the main research components and objectives being represented by visual icons (such as the radioactivity sign, wireless communication etc). Additionally, the RAMONES objectives also have their own image, as shown below.

Figure 34 RAMONES logos for its thematic objectives.

Furthermore, for significant events, such as Season’s holidays, etc. special designs have been provided.

Figure 35 The RAMONES Christmas card sent in December 2021 to a large number of recipients.

2.2.2 Document templates

The WP5 team has produced a set of templates for various documents and activities. All of them are maintained and updated according to the needs, being available in the common RAMONES Google Drive, as illustrated in the figure below:

Name	Owner	Last modified	File size
RAMONES-Deliverable-Documents_Template.docx	me	30 Apr 2021 Theo Mertzimekis	293 KB
RAMONES-Effort-Reporting_Template.xlsx	me	30 Apr 2021 Theo Mertzimekis	99 KB
RAMONES-Meeting-Minutes_Template.docx	me	30 Apr 2021 Theo Mertzimekis	133 KB
RAMONES-Presentation_Template.pptx	me	2 Nov 2021 me	1.1 MB
RAMONES-Presentation_TemplateV1.key	Theo Mertzimekis	30 Apr 2021 Theo Mertzimekis	8.9 MB
RAMONES-Presentation_TemplateV2.key	Theo Mertzimekis	30 Apr 2021 Theo Mertzimekis	7.9 MB
RAMONES-Qnn-PartnerID-Progress-Report_Template.docx	me	14 Jul 2021 me	71 KB

Figure 36 Document templates on RAMONES Google Drive.

The RAMONES team have been trained to use them to maximize the impact of dissemination to various audiences. The application of the templates includes the following:

- Deliverables
- Report activities.
- Meetings
- Project presentations
- Baseline text for specific purposes (mailings, invitations, etc) related to any special need proposed by the project team.

In all templates, the project graphics are applied as appropriate, customizing for particular purposes when necessary.

The next figure illustrates a “.pptx” template to be used in any activity related to the project. The current document is another example, edited from a project “.docx” template. Additional templates have been created for other types of software (e.g. Keynote).

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Figure 37 RAMONES Template for presentations.

2.2.3 Dissemination material

The WP has produced, delivered and updated baseline generic content in the form of banners, leaflets and textual components. All the material templates are available on the project-shared Google Drive. Following are some samples materialized:

RAMONES

RAMONES ambition is to bring together innovative technology and recent advancements in sensory materials, low-power autonomous robotic systems, and state-of-the-art modelling techniques to overcome current limitations in performing in situ and in near-real time underwater radioactivity measurements at large spatiotemporal scales.

Objectives

1. Design, develop and validate novel instrumentation towards a holistic marine radioactivity detection and monitoring.
2. Design, develop, and validate the efficacy of multiple cooperative robotic systems endowed with self-deployment and self-awareness capabilities and equipped with new marine radioactivity instrumentation to adaptively monitor radioactivity levels of extended volumes of the ocean.
3. Design and implement intensive integration and adequate validation activities in a step-wise approach to provide reliable data, form policies and strengthen the resilience of EU coastal communities and ecosystems.
4. Design and develop novel methods and algorithms for data calibration/rectification, multimodal data analysis for information extraction, as well as modelling for critical environmental monitoring tasks.
5. Establish a visual and textual identity of the project and its work and maximise the impactful visibility of projects work and achievements relying on Open Access and FAIR principles.
6. Design a new blueprint for Environmental Intelligence in EU.

Consortium

Hellenic Republic
National and Kapodistrian
University of Athens

INSTITUT ROYAL
D'HYDROLOGIE ET
MÉTÉOROLOGIE

EvoLogics

ENS | PSL

UNIVERSITY OF
ATHENS

PLOATECH

Durham
UNIVERSITY

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Social Media

@ramones_eu

RAMONES receives funding from European Union under Horizon 2020 FET-Prosper Programme via grant agreement No. 101017060

Figure 38 RAMONES banner.

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Figure 39 RAMONES leaflet.

The dissemination material was also deployed in meetings and face-to-face events, thus helping to consolidate the project's brand. Unfortunately, the impact of the global COVID-19 pandemic limited this type of activities, with digital documents being the main dissemination and promotion tool. Figures below show some dissemination material used in face-to-face events.

Figure 40 Dissemination and branding material for face-to-face events (1).

Details on the dissemination materials could also be found in D5.14.

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Figure 41 Dissemination and branding material for face-to-face events (2)

2.3 Articles and publications

Articles of general interest may be distributed over the press, other media sites or the web site of the project. Articles and publication production includes general purpose articles, press and media content, and scientific publications. The primary language is English, in order to reach the widest potential audience. However, the languages spoken in the project have been used according to the specific scope, publishing in other languages too. The website is the natural place to host all the work generated.

2.3.1 Articles of general and scientific purpose

The project has appeared in four (4) articles of general interest that were distributed over the on-line press, the first one in the largest-circulation newspaper in Greece, “Kathimerini”, in both its Greek and English editions.

<https://ramones-project.eu/kathimerini-newspaper-has-a-full-coverage-of-the-ramones-project/>

The second article concerning the RAMONES objectives was published in the worldwide edition of the online Media service, VICE, on May 24th, 2021, in the link:

<https://www.vice.com/en/article/88nq84/scientists-want-to-smell-ocean-radiation-to-predict-tsunamis?fbclid=IwAR2RdAvW1J3toGY1m9JegY6LaRF0dOncp7Wx0MPGYRkCUWshHbZ9OB9zROY>

The third public article appeared on EU H2020 News concerning the launch of the RAMONES project in the European Projects ecosystems whereas the fourth public article appeared again on EU H2020 News focusing on the Environmental Intelligence framework.

The fourth public-interest article, a specialized article related to the RAMONES project under the title ‘Ocean Radioactivity and its impact on the world’, was published in the tenth issue of IMPACT magazine from Durham University (Business School). The digital issue of IMPACT, with the theme of Sustainability and Society, was launched on Monday 29.11.2021 (https://issuu.com/durhambusinessschool/docs/impact_magazine_issue_10)

The articles of scientific interest are 2 journal papers, 4 Peer reviewed papers and 6 Peer reviewed Conference papers:

Journal Papers (Peer reviewed)

1. N. Hung, A. Pascoal, F. Rego, '*Cooperative distributed estimation and control of multiple autonomous vehicles for range-based underwater target localization and pursuit*', IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology, Sept. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TCST.2021.3107346
2. D. Santos, P. Batista, P. Oliveira, C. Silvestre, '*Decentralized navigation systems for bearing-based position and velocity estimation in tiered formations*', International Journal of Systems Science, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.1080/00207721.2021.1961916
3. T.J. Mertzimekis, C. Andrikopoulos, C. Fakiola, A. Kotsovolou, D. Lampridou, S. Kazana, '*Development and characterization of a mobile γ -spectrometer and its field deployment for in situ radioactivity measurements*', Nuclear Energy and Technology, 24 June 2021, doi: 10.3897/nucet.7.60122
4. A. Dura, T.J. Mertzimekis, P. Nomikou, A. Gondikas, M.M. Gómez Míguez, E. Bakalis, F. Zerbetto, '*The Hydrothermal Vent Field at the Eastern Edge of the Hellenic Volcanic Arc: The Avyssonos Caldera (Nisyros)*', Geosciences, 13 June 2021, doi: 10.3390/geosciences11070290

Conference Papers (peer reviewed)

5. T.J. Mertzimekis, P. Nomikou, E. Petra, P. Batista, D. Cabesinhas, A. Pascoal, L. Sebastiao, K. Karantzalos, J. Escartin, K. Kebkal, A. Mallios, K. Nikolopoulos, L. Maigne, '*Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems (RAMONES)*', Proceedings of the ACM International Conference on Information Technology for Social Good, Rome, Italy, September 2021, pp. 216-220, doi: 10.1145/3462203.3475906
6. F. Rego, A. Pascoal, '*Cooperative single-beacon multiple AUV navigation under stringent communication bandwidth constraints*', Proc. 13th IFAC Conference on Control Applications in Marine Systems, Robotics, and Vehicles (CAMS), Sept. 22-24, Oldenburg, Germany, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2021.10.096
7. R. Rego, N. Hung, A. Pascoal, '*Cooperative Motion Control Using Hybrid Acoustic-Optical Communication Networks*', Proc. 13th IFAC Conference on Control Applications in Marine Systems, Robotics, and Vehicles (CAMS), Sept. 22-24, Oldenburg, Germany, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2021.10.098
8. M. Jacinto, A. Potes, D. Souto, Y. Gongy, J. Quintas, J. Cruz, S. Garg, A. Pascoal, '*Underwater Geophysical Navigation using a Particle Filter Approach to Multi-Sensor Fusion*', Proc. Oceans 2021 San Diego-Porto, Sept. 2021, doi: not available yet
9. T. Berry, A. Pascoal, '*The Use of Bézier Curves for Optimal Motion Planning of Autonomous Vehicles*', Proc. 5th International Young Engineers Forum on Electrical and Computer Engineering, Caparica (Portugal), July 9, 2021., doi: not available yet

10. P. Mendes and P. Batista, " A study on cooperative navigation of AUVs based on bearing measurements," Proceedings of the Global OCEANS 2021 San Diego – Porto, San Diego, California, USA, September 2021, doi: not available yet

In addition to scientific articles, two (2) MSc and one (1) PhD thesis supported by the IST-ID team addressing topics that were inspired by the scopes of the RAMONES project were published. The authors and the specific info of the specific thesis are listed below:

1. The Nguyen Hung, "Cooperative Control and Estimation of Multi-Agent Systems under Communication Constraints," PhD thesis, IST-Univ. Lisbon, Portugal, defended 13 July, 2021
2. Marcelo Jacinto, "Cooperative Motion Control of Aerial and Marine Vehicles for Environmental Applications," MSc thesis, IST-Univ. Lisbon, Portugal, submitted Oct. 2021
3. Pedro Mendes, "Bearings-based Cooperative Navigation for Arbitrary Formation Topologies," MSc thesis, IST-Univ. Lisbon, Portugal, defended 12 December, 2021

2.3.2 Invited talks and lectures

The invited lectures listed below include topics that were inspired by and cover many of the topics addressed in the scope of the RAMONES project:

1. A. Pascoal, "Cooperative Marine Robots: From Theory to Scientific and Commercial Applications," 1st International Conference on Emerging Electronics & Automation (E&A) 2021, Silchar, India, Dec. 17-19, 2021.
2. A. Pascoal, "Cooperative Marine Robots: Theory and Practice," Genova Blue District-World Oceans Day, Seminar on Marine Robotics, Genova, Italy, 14 Sept. 2021
3. A. Pascoal, "WP6:JRA Innovation to advance marine robotics", in the scope of a EUMR session presented at the EMRA 2021 Workshop on EU-funded Marine Robotics and Applications, July 17-18, Pisa, Italy
4. A. Pascoal, "Ocean Exploration and Mapping using Networked Robotics Vehicles: The EU WiMUST and RAMONES projects", Meeting with Science and Technology, an organization of the Ministry of Science and Technology, June 28-30, Lisbon, Portugal
5. L. Sebastião, "Robotic Systems for Ocean Exploration", 2021 Blue School Lisbon Regional Meeting, 26th Feb. 2021. Dissemination of research activities in front of an audience of teachers involved in the national program "Blue School", fostering Ocean Literacy in the school context.
6. T.J. Mertzimekis, "The RAMONES project and Environmental Intelligence" (2021). A talk with four different versions addressing the relation of the project to the joint Environmental Intelligence initiative and the main objectives, presented in the four different Kick-off meetings (SmartLagoon, WatchPlant, ReSET and iSeed) (Jan and Feb 2021)

7. T.J. Mertzimekis, “RAMONES @ BlueRIDays”, 23 Apr 2021, Blue Research and Innovation Days (online)
8. T.J. Mertzimekis, “Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems”, 8 July 2021, EMRA2021 (online)
9. Theo J. Mertzimekis, Paraskevi Nomikou, Eleni Petra, Antonio Pascoal, Konstantin Kebkal, Javier Escartín, Karantzalos, Konstantinos, Aggelos Mallios, Konstantinos Nikolopoulos, Lydia Maigne, RAMONES: Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems, ICRP2020, International Conference (Dec. 2020)

2.4 Events and activities

RAMONES has communicated, disseminated, got involved and interacted, both with the EU and the EIC ecosystem, more specifically, as well as with the general public, through many activities that, due to the global COVID-19 pandemic of 2021, have been carried out mainly through digital channels. Among them, the following can be included: fairs, congresses, conferences, workshops, webinars.

All of them have been reported on the RAMONES website (considering the goals, the challenges, the work carried out and the results) and disseminated through the RAMONES digital channels.

2.4.1 Conferences and workshops (co)-organized or participated by RAMONES

The most relevant workshops and conferences (co)-organized or participated by the RAMONES team, reported and disseminated through all RAMONES digital channels during this period:

Table 2 Workshops and conferences (co)organised or participated by RAMONES.

Event Name	Type of event	RAMONES role	Place & Date
Blue Research & Innovation Days BRID	Conference	(co) organization	Online, 19-23/5/2021
International Symposium on IoT & ML for Ecosystem Restoration & Multi-hazard Resilience 2021 - ISIM iSIM2021	Symposium	participation	Online, 5-9/6/2021
La celebration de 50 ans de l'IN2P3 au LPC de Clermont Ferrand 50 ans de IN2P3	Workshop	participation	Online, 18/6/2021
EMRA 2021 - Workshop on EU-funded Marine Robotics and Applications EMRA2021	Workshop	(co)organization	Online, 7-9/7/2021

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Event Name	Type of event	RAMONES role	Place & Date
GoodIT ACM International Conference on Information Technology for Social Good GoodIT	Conference	(co) organization	6-9/9/2021
The 29th Annual Symposium of the Hellenic Nuclear Physics Society HNPS2021 - Session focused on “Environmental Intelligence and Emerging Technologies”	Conference	(co) organization	24-25/9/2021

Figure 42 Blue Research and Innovation Days.

2.4.2 Fairs and exhibitions participated

RAMONES actively participated in the International Fair of Thessaloniki 2021.

RAMONES representatives attended the [International Fair of Thessaloniki 2021](#) during the exhibition days where they were linked with the more than 30 projects and research Centers’ representatives that participated in the International Fair with RAMONES, as well as with the visitors to the event. Some synergies with other projects and initiatives have been identified and a productive collaboration may be realized in near future.

Figure 43 RAMONES picture of International Fair participation.

RAMONES partners as project representatives have also participated in the [Ocean Business 2021](#), an Exhibition and Training Forum, a ‘free event for everyone in the ocean science and technology community’. In the specific event multiple innovations at the forefront of the ground-breaking ocean technology are presented every year.

Figure 44 RAMONES picture of Ocean Business 2021 participation.

RAMONES partner's (IST-ID) many representatives (L. Sebastião, D. Cabecinhas, J. Quintas, D. Souto, M. Jacinto, F. Rego) participated in "FIC.A 2021, International Science Festival," from 12-17 October 2021, in Oeiras, Portugal. This festival was the first International Science Festival in Portugal. It was the first edition of an event that was born within the science and technology developed in Portugal and is projected to the world in a groundbreaking way, with a strong commitment to education, culture, and art.

The FIC.A program presented various areas of science, technology, culture, and art, from health and medicine, through the environment, archeology, to astronomy and artificial intelligence, or even areas such as sports and gastronomy. The schedule included activities for audiences of all ages and is free of charge.

Figure 45 RAMONES pictures of FIC.A 2021 participation.

2.4.3 Other events organized/attended

As has been described above, RAMONES presented invited talks and courses in other events such as:

1. The Blue School Lisbon Regional Meeting, Lisbon, 26th Feb. 2021
2. “We need to Talk about Kevin”, Keynote speech, Centre for innovation and technology management (CITM), Doctoral conference (30 attendees), Durham University, 14 June 2021 (30 attendees)
3. The ‘Meeting with Science and Technology’ event, organized by the Ministry of Science and Technology, June 28-30, Lisbon, Portugal
4. “Ocean Exploration using Marine Robotic Systems: Science and Technology”, by A. Pascoal, a 3-hour module presented during the international ULISSES Summer Course organized by the University of Lisbon under the initiative Interdisciplinary Studies on Sustainable Environment and Seas, IST, Lisbon, July 2021
5. “Cooperative Motion Planning, Navigation, and Control of Networked Marine Robots: Theory and Practice”, by A. Pascoal, a 2 hour online short course offered on occasion of the DTU Marine Robotics Summer School, Lyngby, Denmark, 27 August 2021.
6. Genova Blue District-World Oceans Day with a ‘Seminar on Marine Robotics’, Genova, Italy, 14 Sept. 2021
7. School of Geography f2f and streamed online Seminar for the Institute of Hazard Risk and Resilience, IHRR Seminar 4th October, (<https://fclubb.github.io/>), Durham University (40 attendees)
8. “Open Day, IST-Tagus Park Campus” Portugal, Nov. 6, 2021
9. Four Kick-off meetings organized by the EUC-funded projects participating in the Environmental Intelligence Consortium.
10. SANTORY Project Kick-Off Meeting, Sep. 2021

Figure 46 RAMONES presentation at ‘Meeting with Science and Technology’.

Figure 47 RAMONES pictures of Open Day Exhibit participation.

2.4.4 Meetings

The RAMONES team held many meetings, mainly by teleconference. The Kick-off Meeting was held on 8-9 March 2021 via teleconference and a blended general meeting of RAMONES in 9 and 10 of November 2021 was held in person, once travel restrictions due to covid19 pandemic were lifted. Several other meetings with relevant stakeholders, presenting RAMONES and discussing innovation, business and the challenges of new technology and services to keep up-to-date and enrich the knowledge about the scope of the project, being the RAMONES digital channels, a fruitful point of contact.

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Figure 48 RAMONES kick-off teleconference.

Figure 49 RAMONES workshop (1).

2.5 Relevant H2020 Projects & other projects liaised with RAMONES

As described earlier, four (4) projects are liaised with RAMONES, from the same Call (Environmental Intelligence projects), sharing experiences and solutions to challenges. These are: RESET, WatchPlant, SmartLagoon, and iSeed.

RAMONES is closely connected to them, working on joint activities, additionally exploring synergies, potential future collaborations, but also investing time and effort to set the major guidelines for Environmental Intelligence in Europe. The give projects have committed time, effort and funding to collaborate and attempt to produce a blueprint for Environmental Intelligence for the next decades.

Figure 50 Projects from the same Call, liaised with RAMONES.

WatchPlant

Main facts and achievements:

- RAMONES and WatchPlant consortia were introduced to each other and discussed the context of future collaboration as well as working towards completing the planned joint activities. Both projects share environmental aspects under an innovative approach, thus offering grounds for future collaboration.
- There were mutual Invitations and participation in each other's Kick-Off Meetings
- Proposition for an organization of a common webinar and training activities

iSeed

Main facts and achievements:

- RAMONES and iSeed consortia were introduced to each other and discussed the context of future collaboration as well as working towards completing the planned joint activities. Both projects share objectives on developing robotic technologies to address serious environmental problems, thus offering grounds for future collaboration.
- Mutual Invitations and participation in each other's Kick-Off Meetings

- Proposition for an organization of a common webinar and training activities

SmartLagoon

Main facts and achievements:

- RAMONES and SmartLagoon consortia were introduced to each other and discussed the context of future collaboration as well as working towards completing the planned joint activities. As the focus of both projects is in the aqueous environment (lagoon, ocean) some common grounds for collaboration have been identified and will be explored further in the future.
- Mutual Invitations and participation in each other's Kick-Off Meetings
- Proposition for an organization of a common webinar and training activities

ReSET

Main facts and achievements:

- RAMONES and ReSET consortia were introduced to each other and discussed the context of future collaboration as well as working towards completing the planned joint activities. As the focus of both projects is on innovative sensor technologies, some common grounds for collaboration have been identified and will be explored further in the future.
- Mutual Invitations and participation in each other's Kick-Off Meetings
- Proposition for an organization of a common webinar and training activities

2.5.2 Other Relevant H2020 Projects liaised with RAMONES

In addition, there are relevant H2020 Projects and research infrastructures liaised with RAMONES:

Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no1

Figure 51 Other Relevant H2020 Projects & research infrastructures liaised with RAMONES.

RAMONES is continuously linked with these projects and initiatives, being aware of prospective projects and the activities that we advertise and participate in, mainly those related to Underwater, Radioactivity and EI research, as well as the computer technologies that allow the development of prediction and services.

Figure 52 Affiliated projects with RAMONES.

OPENAIRE (RI)

www.openaire.eu/openaire-project

OPENAIRE aims to shift scholarly communication towards openness and transparency and facilitate innovative ways to communicate and monitor research by means of Align policies, Provide open science services, Link research, Monitor (open) science, Train for open science, Build global bridges and Facilitate Open Innovation.

INFORE

<https://www.infore-project.eu/>

The aim of the INFORE project is to address the challenges posed by huge datasets and pave the way for real-time, interactive extreme-scale analytics and forecasting.

Blue-Cloud

<https://www.blue-cloud.org/>

Blue-Cloud is a European H2020 project with the overarching aim of federating and piloting innovative services for Marine Research and the Blue Economy. The project is working towards the establishment of a marine-thematic EOSC serving the Blue Economy, Marine Environment and Marine Knowledge agendas.

3. WP5 Organization related to Dissemination /Communication

3.1 Coordination Model

The OTF is formed by the Outreach and Communication representatives of every RAMONES partner in order to lead and coordinate Dissemination activities. The composition of the OTF is based on the Grant Agreement and is led by the WP5 leader related to Communication and outreach activities and materials.

The role of the team is to monitor outreach activities, identify opportunities and mobilize resources, as outreach in RAMONES is quite intensive, ambitious and of strategic importance for the success of the project. WP5 is composed of all project members, who were requested to contribute with their knowledge and networking, as well as the specific tasks in charge.

4. Summary

As a conclusion, the following table summarizes the indicators of success of the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities. The details are presented in the Report of Activities section above.

Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no1

1. KPI's concerning user (supply and demand) attraction:

Table 3 KPIs concerning user (supply and demand) attraction for the overall project timeline.

Range	Type of dissemination and communication activities	Target	Contributed values	Accomplished
Ecosystem	Workshops / conferences (co)organized.	6	5	83%
Ecosystem	Workshops supported by presenters and panelists on project specific topics.	14	8	57%

2. KPIs concerning scientific dissemination:

Table 4 KPIs concerning scientific dissemination for the overall project timeline.

Range	Type of dissemination and communication activities	Target	Contributed values	Accomplished
Wide range	Average social media posts per month	2	4	200%
Wide range	General public articles languages supported	4	2	50%
Ecosystem	Peer reviewed scientific publications	10	14	140%
Ecosystem	Other scientific publications and artifacts	12	14	116%
Ecosystem	References and acknowledgements	50	25	50%
Ecosystem	Whitepapers (as per work plan)	3	0	0
Ecosystem	Multimedia & training material published	8	3	38%
Ecosystem	Gold Open Access publications percentage	>70%	85%	121%
Wide range	Fairs and exhibitions participated	3	3	100%
Wide range	Commercial exploitation events participation	5	2	40%

3. KPIs concerning social dissemination:

Table 5 KPIs concerning social dissemination for the overall project timeline.

Range	Type of dissemination and communication activities	Target	Contributed values	Accomplished
Wide range	Websites launched (workplan)	1	1	100%
Wide range	Website content updating (average)	monthly	monthly	100%
Ecosystem	Templates for dissemination activities and other material	2	2	100%
Ecosystem	Hardcopy/tangible material forms	3	8	266%
Wide range	Social media dissemination channels	4	5	125%

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Wide range	Social media impressions (social media channels total)	10,000	20902	209%
Wide range	Social media followers (total across media)	1200	676	56%
Wide range	Average technical blog posts per year	2	2	100%
Wide range	Average general public blog posts per year	6	5	83%
Wide range	General public articles on printed or online media	8	5	62%
Wide range	Newsletters issued (biannual)	8	2	25%

4. KPIs concerning strengthen impact via joint efforts:

Table 6 KPIs concerning strengthen impact via joint efforts for the overall project timeline.

Range	Type of dissemination and communication activities	Target	Contributed values	Accomplished
Ecosystem	Relevant H2020 Projects & other projects liaised with RAMONES	6	7	116%
Ecosystem	MoUs signed with 3rd parties.	5	2	40%
Ecosystem	Datathons/hackathons organized by the project	2	0	0
Ecosystem	3rd party datathons/hackathons supported by project	2	0	0
Ecosystem	Datathons/hackathons participants	200	0	0
Ecosystem	Individuals directly addressed via scientific, academic communication, innovation stimulation, training and engagement activities	1800	13637	757%